

ANALYSING CHILDREN'S SPEAKING SKILLS BY USING PERSONAL EXPERIENCE.

Bahromova Munisa Otabekovna

Termez State University Foreign Philology Faculty the 2nd course student.

@munisabahromova1@gmail.com , +99890 644 79 09

Abstract: The skills and development of children's language are unique to observe, the researchers found several cases of varying language abilities in the age range of 6-12 years old who are still in primary school. From the perspective of child development psychology, the findings are influenced by several factors that are directly or indirectly related to the child's life. On the basis of this background, the researchers made an analysis of the results of observation of primary school children in the age range of 6-12 years with the object of research made randomly. The result of the data obtained by the researcher is that the elementary school age children have significant differences in the ability to speak in the school environment and outside the school environment.

Keys words: Analysis, Language Skills, Primary School, varying language.

The matter of this research is based on the diversity of the initial ability of elementary school students in the school environment, it is much influenced by the family environment, the community where the child lives. Many researchers conducted empirical observations in the field so that it was considered unique from various aspects of elementary school age children. The community where a primary school-age child life is mixed on many factors that influence the abilities and thinking skills of these elementary school-age children. Family and the variety of ways and speaking styles of family members influence many children's skills and communication skills even though family factors are only one of many influencing factors. The community of communication and ethnic diversity in terms of sociolinguistics is the strongest influence to shape the abilities and speaking skills of an elementary school child. The capacity to talk or communicate in the target language accurately, fluently, and extensively is one of the language abilities that any learner of a foreign language must acquire. By speaking, a student may express their ideas, suggestions, opinions, and interests. Speaking also increases their awareness of the outside world. A worldwide language is especially English. But English is also thought to be hard to learn. Speaking requires a variety of abilities, including pronunciation, sentence structure (grammar), and vocabulary. The majority of EFL students find it challenging to enhance their English-speaking skills since they are used to using their mother tongue in everyday life, according to several

study findings. Speaking is also verbal language in spoken form. Many effective skill exercises fall short of expectations because the subject matter is inappropriate or the students are unfamiliar with the material .

Children's language skills in their development can be seen and assessed directly from the child's speaking ability in various social situations, because it is very possible that there are different ways and styles of speaking for different situations and interlocutors. The speaking skills referred to by the researcher are a language skill that develops in a child's life, which is only preceded by listening skills, and at that time the ability to speak or speak is learned . Many things are related to language development in children, especially with regard to language development in elementary school-age children which includes (1)

the nature of language development; (2) children's language development; (3) development of oral communication; (4) development of written communication; and (5) the development of reading and writing

Preschool childhood attracts linguists because the subject (child's speech) is linguistically versatile and interesting. According to linguist scientists, every fact about children's speech can be considered in at least two directions and must: 1) as temporary speech on the way to "adult language" (if we are talking about innovation Isa); 2) As an element of the child's autonomous language system, the child has a certain functional task within it.

A reliable psychological-linguistic justification of methodological issues of children's speech development is considered a characteristic of modern pedagogical research. These studies, carried out in the spirit of the best traditions of Russian pedagogy, will have a large factual material, determine the objective laws of the child's speech. Using the classification of F.A. Sokhin and O.S. Ushakov, the psychological-pedagogical research of children's speech can be divided into three directions: structural (formation of various structural levels of the language system: phonetic, lexical, grammatical levels), functional (formation of language acquisition skills in communicative activity); cognitive (forming a simple understanding of language and speech phenomena).

The analysis of the phenomenon of "child's speech development" and the process of its management leads to the conclusion that pedagogues need to undergo special training to work in the field of speech development of preschool children.

Modern research on speech has a systematic approach, which is reflected in the study of the phenomenon of "many external and internal relations that exist as a single system" (B.F. Lomov). The speech-language system engages in many interactions, including the semantic information apparatus that translates meaning into words and is

intrinsically linked to human consciousness and emotions, psychophysical phenomena (i.e., brain activity, physical sounds the device that generates and receives and classifies them), means of communication and social communication are their main ones. First, let's turn to the concept of "speech". Analysis of general approaches to speech as an object of scientific research allows us to draw conclusions about the extreme complexity and versatility of this phenomenon, the study of which is extremely important for understanding all aspects of mental development. "Speech as a unique activity does not stand alongside other types of activity, it occupies a central place in the process of psychological development..." (A.N. Leontiev).

By comparing these approaches that describe the language from different points of view, it is possible to distinguish the general features of speech as an object of scientific study.

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